

Supplementary Material

Slow modulation of the contraction patterns in *Physarum polycephalum*

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I. MATERIALS AND METHODS

A. Experimental system culture and insemination

FIG. 1: Bright field colour image of a *Physarum polycephalum* specimen confined into three concentric annuli by plastic rings (outer ring transparent, two inner rings black). The three ring-shaped plasmodia are highlighted in green, blue and orange. Inoculation points used to transfer growing fronts are visible on the outer agar.

Experiments were conducted on *Physarum polycephalum* in its plasmodial stage, obtained as sclerotia (Carolina Biological, USA). Plasmodia were grown on Petri dishes half filled with Phytigel-based gels, containing glucose kept at a sufficiently low concentration to avoid bias caused by chemotaxis. Gels are composed of 2% Phytigel, 1% glucose, and can include 2% oatmeal agar, to test nutrient availability effect [1]. No systematic differences were observed when adding oatmeal. Cultures were fed with sterilized oat flakes and kept at 25°C in darkness. Once or twice per week, the growing front was transferred to fresh gel. After 10–20 h of recovery and spreading, ring-shaped plasmodia were prepared by punching concentric annuli with thin plastic rings, which remained in place to prevent fusion (see Figure 1). This procedure defined annuli with perimeters $L = 6.0\text{--}13.6$ cm and aspect ratios $L/e = 11\text{--}41$, where e is annulus width. Dishes were sealed and maintained at

25°C with heating plates during recordings. Transmitted light microscopy video is started after a typical settling time of 15–30 minutes.

B. Image acquisition

Ring plasmodia were imaged in transmitted light using a Leica Z16 APO macroscope with TL5000 LED base (440–650 nm) and a CMOS Basler acA2440-75uc color camera. Intensity has been dimmed at its maximum to ensure that it does not elicit a specific response from the plasmodium: the emitted light intensity was 11 ± 0.5 lux, at least 10 times lower than the reported phototaxis threshold [2–5]. RGB images were recorded every 4–6 s with ~ 500 ms exposure, $37 \mu\text{m}/\text{pixel}$ resolution (2448×2048 pixels), for total film durations of 4–15 h. All experiments were conducted in a light-tight enclosure.

C. Beer-Lambert law

To relate transmitted intensity to cytoplasm thickness, we placed plasmodium samples in a custom-built glass wedge chamber of controlled gradient thickness. Intensity measurements were fitted with the Beer–Lambert law,

$$I = I_0 e^{-h/\ell_a}, \quad (1)$$

yielding absorption lengths $\ell_a \simeq 100 \mu\text{m}$ (blue), $200 \mu\text{m}$ (green), and $350 \mu\text{m}$ (red), which vary slightly due to the aging of *Physarum* pigments. These values are consistent with measurements ($\ell_a \simeq 67 \mu\text{m}$) reported by Bykov et al. [6] obtained with a Doppler optical coherence tomography technique with an infrared (840 nm) super luminescent diode. The blue channel, providing highest sensitivity, was used in subsequent analysis.

D. Signal analysis

Height variations were obtained from transmitted intensity using the Beer–Lambert calibration (blue channel). The signal was smoothed with a 10-frame (~ 60 s)

top-hat filter to remove high-frequency noise. At each position, the height was decomposed as

$$h(t) = D(t) + A(t) \cos \phi(t), \quad (2)$$

where $D(t)$ is the slow baseline drift (vein diameter and network reorganisation), $A(t)$ the oscillation amplitude (modulated on intermediate timescales), and $\phi(t)$ the instantaneous phase (fast contractile state). Signal upper and lower envelopes were extracted by cubic spline interpolation of extrema, defining $h_{\max}(t)$ and $h_{\min}(t)$, respectively. The drift $D(t)$ and amplitude $A(t)$ are then defined as:

$$D(t) = (h_{\max}(t) + h_{\min}(t))/2, \quad (3)$$

$$A(t) = (h_{\max}(t) - h_{\min}(t))/2. \quad (4)$$

The phase $\phi(t)$ was computed as the argument of the analytic signal obtained from the Hilbert transform of $(h - D)/A$ [7]. Values were averaged over an angular sector. Angular sectors are of constant arc length ($\simeq 1.1$ mm) by adjusting the number of sectors N according to the ring perimeter L .

To isolate modulation dynamics from slower network restructuring, we define the drift variation

$$\Delta D = D - \langle D \rangle_{T_D},$$

with moving average window $T_D = 3000$ s which captures vein-diameter changes. To visualise contraction–dilatation asymmetry we define the smoothed residual

$$s(\theta, t) = \langle h - D \rangle_w,$$

where $w = 2.35 T_{\text{osc}}$ corresponds to the FWHM of the Gaussian kernel.

E. Code availability

All image processing, signal decomposition, window detection, and statistical analyses were performed using custom Python scripts developed for this study. The full analysis pipeline, including preprocessing, Hilbert-based decomposition, Fourier mode classification, and correlation analysis, is publicly available in a dedicated data repository (DataDryad; link provided in the manuscript).

II. AUTOMATIC DETECTION OF ROTATING AND STANDING MODES ON A RING

We detail here the algorithm to automatically detect time windows in which coherent spatial Fourier modes emerge. For each experiment, candidate time windows are scanned using sliding segments of duration τ_{\min} . Within each window we compute the spatial Fourier coefficients

$$X_m(t) = \frac{1}{2\pi} \int s(\theta, t) e^{-im\theta} d\theta.$$

where θ is the angular coordinate along the ring and with mode index $m \geq 1$. The instantaneous mode amplitude and unwrapped phase are

$$A_m(t) = |X_m(t)|, \quad \Phi_m(t) = \text{unwrap}(\arg[X_m(t)]). \quad (5)$$

The dominant mode m is defined by maximal fractional power

$$P_m = \frac{\langle |X_m|^2 \rangle}{\sum_k \langle |X_k|^2 \rangle},$$

where the brackets denote temporal averaging within the candidate window. The fractional power in the $\pm m$ pair,

$$\text{frac}_m = \frac{P_m + P_{-m}}{\sum_k P_k}. \quad (6)$$

A candidate window is accepted as mode-visible if

$$\text{frac}_m \geq \text{frac}_m^{\text{thr}} = 0.35, \quad (7)$$

ensuring that mode m carries at least 35% of the total spatial power in the selected interval. This threshold was chosen empirically to ensure that the detected spatial mode carries a substantial fraction of the spatial power while retaining sufficient statistical coverage.

A. Winding velocity and fit-quality gate

Within each candidate window that passes the mode-visibility gate, we estimate the winding velocity by a weighted least-squares linear fit of the unwrapped phase,

$$\Phi_m(t) \approx at + b, \quad (8)$$

with weights $w(t) = A_m(t)^2$, so that time points with low mode amplitude contribute less. The winding speed (in revolutions per second) is

$$v = -\frac{a}{2\pi m}. \quad (9)$$

Uncertainties on a are obtained from the standard error of the linear regression slope:

$$\sigma_a = \sqrt{\frac{\sigma_{\text{res}}^2}{\sum (t_i - \bar{t})^2}},$$

where σ_{res}^2 is the residual variance of the fit. The goodness of fit R^2 is computed from the weighted residuals. Windows are accepted only if

$$R^2 \geq R_{\min}^2 = 0.10. \quad (10)$$

Uncertainty on v is estimated using circular block bootstrap on the phase residuals, yielding a 95% CI.

B. Direction-coherence gate and mode classification

Because the unwrapped phase $\Phi_m(t)$ can exhibit intermittent slips when A_m becomes small, we introduce an increment-based direction-coherence score. We compute wrapped phase increments,

$$\Delta\Phi_m(t) = \arg\left[e^{i(\Phi_m(t+\delta t) - \Phi_m(t))}\right], \quad (11)$$

discarding time points where $A_m(t)$ falls below the 30th percentile. The instantaneous winding estimate is

$$v(t) = -\frac{1}{2\pi m} \frac{\Delta\Phi_m(t)}{\delta t}. \quad (12)$$

We then define the direction-coherence score as

$$p_{\text{dir}} = \max[P(v(t) > 0), P(v(t) < 0)], \quad (13)$$

i.e. the fraction of time during which the instantaneous winding velocity maintains the same sign ($p_{\text{dir}} = 1$: perfectly rotating regime with constant direction, $p_{\text{dir}} = 0.5$: positive and negative increments occur with comparable probability, purely standing regime).

Classification of each accepted window proceeds as follows:

- **Rotating mode:** $|v| > 2 \times 10^{-4}$ rev/s and $p_{\text{dir}} \geq 0.72$, with the minority direction fraction below $0.5 - 0.25/2 = 0.375$ (direction margin = 0.25).
- **High-order mode:** both positive and negative winding directions simultaneously exceed the p_{dir} threshold; the window is labelled as a mixed bi-directional mode.
- **Standing mode:** $|v| \leq 6 \times 10^{-4}$ rev/s and $p_{\text{dir}} \leq 0.65$, only in windows where no rotating evidence is present.

C. Period extraction for standing modes

Because $A \approx |\Delta D|$, the amplitude envelope A oscillates at *half* the drift cycle period T_{std} : each drift cycle produces two amplitude maxima (one for each sign of ΔD). Consequently, the spatial Fourier amplitude $\mathcal{A}_m(t) = |X_m(t)|$ of the slow field $s(\theta, t)$ oscillates at frequency $2/T_{\text{std}}$, so that extracting its dominant FFT peak and multiplying by two recovers T_{std} without bias.

Concretely, for each standing episode we compute $\mathcal{A}_m(t) = |X_m(t)|$ from the slow field evaluated within the episode time window. The dominant period of $\mathcal{A}_m(t)$ is found as the argmax of the power spectrum within the fixed frequency band $[0.001, 0.010]$ Hz (corresponding to $T_{\text{pk}}(A) \in [100, 1000]$ s), and the standing period is

$$T_{\text{std}} = 2T_{\text{pk}}(\mathcal{A}_m), \quad (14)$$

with a 95% confidence interval obtained by circular block bootstrap ($n_{\text{boot}} = 200$ resamples, block length 80 frames)

This approach yields two observable cycles of \mathcal{A}_m per drift cycle, doubling the number of usable cycles relative to an estimator applied directly to ΔD , and avoiding contamination by very slow network-reorganisation drift (periods > 1000 s). The frequency band is fixed (not adaptive), which prevents the FFT from locking onto the $2T_{\text{pk}}$ sub-harmonic that would arise if the search range were set proportionally to the episode's estimated $\langle t_{\text{pk}} \rangle$. FFT argmax on \mathcal{A}_m has been validated to be unbiased on synthetic rectified-sinusoid signals (mean error $< 0.1\%$ for ≥ 2 observable cycles), making it the preferred estimator.

D. Window selection: longest coherent regime

Our goal is to identify the largest interval during which the system remains approximately within a single transport regime. Window selection is therefore hierarchical:

1. Generate candidates over (s, L) and compute $(v, \text{frac}_m, R^2, p_{\text{dir}})$.
2. Apply hard acceptance gates: mode visibility (frac_m threshold), fit quality ($R^2 \geq R_{\text{min}}^2$), and rotation coherence ($p_{\text{dir}} \geq p_{\text{dir}}^{\text{th}}$) for rotating modes.
3. Among passing candidates, select the largest window length L .
4. Break ties using minimal relative uncertainty and maximal linearity.

E. Episode duration statistics and mode families

Episodes were classified into three mode families based on the dominant spatial Fourier mode and phase-drift properties:

- Fundamental rotating modes ($m = 1$),
- High-order modes ($m > 1$),
- Standing modes.

High-order modes comprise travelling patterns with multiple spatial lobes. Within this family, we show two recurrent subtypes:

- *Bi-directional configurations*, where two counter-propagating travelling components coexist within the same window;
- *Complex configurations*, where multiple propagative features with distinct velocities are simultaneously present.

FIG. 2: Episode duration distributions by mode class across all 47 ring experiments (total recording: 482 h). (a) Fundamental rotating modes ($m = 1$; $n = 48$; median 163 min). (b) High-order modes ($m > 1$; $n = 12$; median 92 min). (c) Standing modes ($n = 50$; median 84 min). In all three histograms the dashed vertical line marks the median. (d) Mode-time budget showing total detected time per family and overall detection coverage (54%). Fundamental rotating modes dominate both in number and total duration.

These subtypes are illustrated in Supplementary Figures 6 and 7 but are grouped under the same quantitative category ($m > 1$ travelling) for statistical analysis.

To quantify how long each type of slow-modulation pattern persists, we measured the duration of all detected episodes across the 47 ring experiments (total recording time: 482 h). Figure 2 shows the resulting duration distributions together with the overall mode-time budget.

Rotating $m = 1$ episodes are by far the most prevalent and the longest lived (median 163 min, $n = 48$, accounting for 160 h of detected activity). High-order rotating modes ($m > 1$) are the least common (median 92 min, $n = 12$, 19 h total) and typically arise as transient states between fundamental rotating episodes or during direction reversals. Standing episodes are shorter than rotating modes (median 84 min, $n = 50$, 84 h total) and generally appear as brief transitional regimes between two rotating episodes of opposite direction.

In total, detected episodes cover 263 h out of 482 h of recording time (54% detection coverage). The remaining time consists of unclassified segments, predominantly periods of low-amplitude or spatially incoherent activity, and is not attributed to any specific mode.

III. SIGNAL ANALYSIS: CORRELATION BETWEEN CONTRACTILE OSCILLATIONS, SLOW MODULATION, AND MEAN VEIN DIAMETER

We detail here the quantitative correlations observed between the contractile oscillations $h-D$, the slow amplitude modulation A , and the mean vein diameter proxy ΔD . For ring confined plasmodia the fast contractile oscillations develop dominantly as counter-propagating

waves forming from a source and annihilating at a sink, with a fixed period of $T_{\text{osc}} \approx 100$ s [8]. We show below that the asymmetry of these fast oscillations (between contraction and dilatations) and the locations of source and sink points are spatially correlated with the slow modulation fields, and that all three slow fields (A , ΔD , and source/sink positions) evolve coherently on the slow modulation timescale $T_{\text{sl}} \sim 10^3$ s.

A. Source and sink extraction from isophase contours

To track the instantaneous source and sink positions of the fast contractile oscillation we use the instantaneous phase $\phi(\theta, t)$ obtained from the Hilbert transform of $(h-D)/A$ (see §I.D of the supplementary and Fig. 3).

a. Per-contraction isophase contours (one point per oscillation cycle). We extract the isophase contour $\phi = 0$ in the (θ, t) kymograph using the phase jump $\phi : 2\pi \rightarrow 0$, which traces a closed loop for each oscillation cycle. The source is defined as the angular coordinate corresponding to the earliest time along the closed contour, and the sink as the coordinate at the latest time. This gives one source-sink pair per contraction cycle (~ 120 – 200 s resolution) and is less susceptible to inter-frame noise. Source and sink positions obtained by this method are shown in Figure 3.

B. Representative examples

We present four representative examples illustrating different slow spatio-temporal regimes. For each example we show simultaneously:

FIG. 3: Time series of (a) $h - D$, (b) ϕ . On (a) black and white dots represent source and sink positions obtained from the isophases $\phi = 0$ of the fast oscillations.

- (a) the fast contractile height variations $h - D$, with source (black dots) and sink (white diamonds) positions from Method B overlaid;
- (b) the temporally smoothed height variation or height residual $s(\theta, t)$, which reveals the local asymmetry between contraction and dilatation on slow timescales; red and blue dots mark the spatial maxima and minima of s ;
- (c) the oscillation amplitude $A(\theta, t)$; red and blue dots from panel (b) are reproduced to show their coincidence with amplitude extrema;
- (d) the drift variation ΔD ; black dots mark amplitude maxima from panel (c), highlighting the systematic occurrence of amplitude maxima near zero-crossings of the drift variation (see §III.C).

a. *Fig. 4 — Rotating mode.* A single travelling-wave modulation pattern rotates monotonically around the ring. Source and sink positions precess continuously, consistent with the rotating amplitude maximum. A green dashed line guides the eye along the slow modulation revolution.

b. *Fig. 5 — Standing mode.* Source and sink positions oscillate about fixed angular positions (nodes), consistent with the standing character of the amplitude pattern.

c. *Fig. 6 — High-order (Bi-directional) mode.* A transient mixed state where two counter-rotating modulation patterns coexist, leading to crossing diagonal streaks in the kymograph.

d. *Fig. 7 — High-order (complex) mode.* Multiple propagating features with distinct velocities are simultaneously present, corresponding to several source–sink pairs visible in the fast-oscillation kymograph.

FIG. 4: *Rotating mode*: time series of (a) $h - D$, (b) s (fast oscillations asymmetry), (c) A , and (d) ΔD . On (a) and (b) black dots and white diamonds represent source and sink positions. On (c) red and blue dots correspond to s maxima and minima. On (d) black dots correspond to A maxima showing phase shift between the drift variations and oscillations modulations. Green dashed line is a guide to the eye.

FIG. 5: *Standing mode*: time series of (a) $h - D$, (b) s (fast oscillations asymmetry), (c) A , and (d) ΔD . On (a) and (b) black dots and white diamonds represent source and sink positions. On (c) red and blue dots correspond to s maxima and minima. On (d) black dots correspond to A maxima showing phase shift between the drift variations and oscillations modulations.

FIG. 6: *High-order (Bi-directional) mode*: time series of (a) $h - D$, (b) s (fast oscillations asymmetry), (c) A , and (d) ΔD . On (a) and (b) black dots and white diamonds represent source and sink positions. On (c) red and blue dots correspond to s maxima and minima. On (d) black dots correspond to A maxima showing phase shift between the drift variations and oscillations modulations.

FIG. 7: *High-order (complex) mode*: time series of (a) $h - D$, (b) s (fast oscillations asymmetry), (c) A , and (d) ΔD . On (a) and (b) black dots and white diamonds represent source and sink positions. On (c) red and blue dots correspond to s maxima and minima. On (d) black dots correspond to A maxima showing phase shift between the drift variations and oscillations modulations.

In all four cases the smoothed height variations s are spatially co-localised with regions of high amplitude A , confirming the coupling between oscillation asymmetry and oscillation amplitude (enhanced excitability). Positive height residuals regions coincide systematically with source positions of the fast waves, and negative height residuals regions with sink positions. By comparing maxima and minima of s and ΔD a systematic phase shift is observed across all examples (*in quadrature*), discussed quantitatively in §III.C.

C. Statistical quantification of spatial and temporal correlations

We systematise these observations in this section. We compute for each source point (θ_s, t_s) the angular distance $\Delta\theta$ to the nearest spatial maximum of s , and for each sink point the angular distance to the nearest minimum. We also compute the angular distances between amplitude maxima and the extrema of s . The *nearest* point is defined using the (spatio-temporal) distance $d_{i,j}$ on kymographs between points (θ_i, t_i) and (θ_j, t_j) :

$$d_{i,j} = \sqrt{\left(\frac{d(\theta_i, \theta_j)}{\Theta_m}\right)^2 + \left(\frac{t_i - t_j}{T_m}\right)^2} \quad (15)$$

where $d(\theta_i, \theta_j) = \text{Arg}(e^{i(\theta_i - \theta_j)})$ (angles subtraction), and with $\Theta_m = \pi$, and $T_m = 100$ s respectively representing the expected largest distances (spatial and temporal scales) for close points. Thus, the *nearest* is here defined by the minimum distance $\min_j d_{s,j}$.

The resulting distributions (Fig. 8) of the angular distances $\Delta\theta$ obtained over all experiments are strongly peaked at $\Delta\theta = 0$, confirming the spatial co-localisation. They are well described by a normalised exponential,

$$p(\Delta\theta) = \frac{1}{\theta_{\text{cor}}} \exp\left(-\frac{\Delta\theta}{\theta_{\text{cor}}}\right), \quad \Delta\theta \in [0, \pi], \quad (16)$$

with characteristic angular distances:

- sources – residual maxima: $\theta_{\text{cor}} = 0.86 \pm 0.11$ rad (95% CI);
- sinks – residual minima: $\theta_{\text{cor}} = 1.01 \pm 0.10$ rad;
- amplitude maxima – residual maxima: $\theta_{\text{cor}} = 1.07 \pm 0.11$ rad;
- amplitude maxima – residual minima: $\theta_{\text{cor}} = 0.88 \pm 0.11$ rad.

Under the null hypothesis of random spatial association, the angular distance distribution would be uniform on $[0, \pi]$. The strong peak at small $\Delta\theta$ and the exponential decay clearly reject this null model. The consistent value $\theta_{\text{cor}} \approx 1$ rad across all four pairs indicates that the spatial association is a robust, system-wide property and not an artefact of a particular observable choice.

FIG. 8: Normalised histograms of $\Delta\theta$ the angular distance between (a) sources and maxima of s , and sinks and the corresponding minima, and (b) amplitude maxima and maxima and minima of s . The resulting probability density functions pdf are fitted by normalised exponential functions giving a characteristic angular distance of (a) $\theta_{\text{cor}} = 0.86 \pm 0.11$ radians for sources-max distances distribution, 1.01 ± 0.10 radians for sinks-min distances, and (b) 1.07 ± 0.11 radians for amplitude-maxima distances and 0.88 ± 0.11 radians for amplitude-minima (errors bars are errors on the fit, CI 95%).

a. Phase relationship between amplitude and drift (Fig. 9). We quantify the temporal relationship between A and ΔD by computing, at each angular position θ and for each maximum of $A(\theta, t)$, the time elapsed to the nearest zero-crossing of $\Delta D(\theta, t)$ (i.e. the nearest time at which ΔD changes sign). This time delay δt is normalised by the instantaneous period $T_{\text{sl}}(t) = 1/f_{\text{sl}}(t)$ of the slow modulation signal, where $f_{\text{sl}}(t)$ is obtained via a second Hilbert transform of s (typically $T_{\text{sl}} \approx 10^3$ s):

$$f_{\text{sl}}(t) = \frac{\omega_{\text{sl}}(\theta, t)}{2\pi}, \quad \omega_{\text{sl}}(\theta, t) = \partial_t \tilde{\Phi}_{\text{sl}}(\theta, t), \quad (17)$$

where $\tilde{\Phi}_{\text{sl}}$ is the unwrapped instantaneous phase from the second Hilbert transform. To obtain a robust global estimate on the ring, we perform an amplitude-weighted spatial average (space is periodic and the sum is taken over the full domain)

$$f_{\text{sl}}(t) = \frac{\int A_{\text{sl}}(\theta, t) f_{\text{sl}}(\theta, t) d\theta}{\int A_{\text{sl}}(\theta, t) d\theta},$$

where $A_{\text{sl}}(\theta, t)$ is the extracted amplitude from the second Hilbert Transform. Noise is suppressed by lightly smoothing $f_{\text{sl}}(t)$ using a small Gaussian kernel ($\sigma = 3\delta t$ with $\delta t = 4 - 6$ s). This procedure gives a continuous, amplitude-weighted measure of the instantaneous period of the slow modulation signal given by $T_{\text{sl}}(t) = 1/f_{\text{sl}}(t)$.

The resulting distribution of $\Delta T/T_{\text{sl}}$ is shown in Fig. 9 and shows a strong peak around 0. As before, it is well described by a normalised exponential with characteristic delay

$$\frac{\delta t_c}{T_{\text{sl}}} = 0.157 \pm 0.007 \quad (95\% \text{ CI}). \quad (18)$$

This typical correlation time $\delta t_c \approx 150$ s corresponds to 1 – 2 fast oscillations periods. This procedure provides a robust estimate of the instantaneous slow modulation period $T_{\text{sl}}(t)$ averaged over the ring. Amplitude maxima occur systematically near zero-crossings of the drift variation, indicating that the envelope is synchronised with sign changes of the slow drift rather than with its extrema. This relation is consistent with the empirical observation $A \approx |\Delta D|$, which naturally implies a doubling of the dominant spectral period between the two signals.

FIG. 9: Normalised histograms of $\Delta T/T_{\text{sl}}$ the rescaled time delay between maxima of amplitudes and zeros of drift variations ΔD , where T_{sl} are the instantaneous time period $T_{\text{sl}}(t) = 1/f(t)$ obtained through Hilbert transform of s (typically $T_{\text{sl}}(t) \approx 1000$ s). The resulting probability density function pdf are fitted by normalised exponential functions and gives a characteristic rescaled time delay $\delta t_c/T_{\text{sl}} = 0.157 \pm 0.007$ (errors bars are errors on the fit, CI 95%).

IV. SUPPLEMENTARY FIGURES

Additional examples illustrating transitions between regimes and the effect of architectural damage are shown in Supplementary Figures 10, 11, and 12.

Rotation direction switch

FIG. 10: Height variations $h - D$, amplitude A and drift ΔD mapping over angle and time, showing a rotating pattern that abruptly changes rotation direction.

Signals for cut organisms

FIG. 11: (a) Bright-field image of a ring with a cut section (red dashed circle). (b) Time series of $h - D$, A , and ΔD : loss of long-range spatio-temporal coordination for architectural damage.

Signals for dying/drying organisms

FIG. 12: (a) Bright-field image of a ring with a dying/drying section (red dashed circle). (b) Corresponding $h - D$, A , and ΔD : loss of long-range modulation when a region dries or dies.

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